

Suppl. Fig. S3-1 (related to Fig. 4S). **Detection and characterization of an endocrine-exocrine lesion mixture in human donor pancreas** (CgA⁺, PGP9.5⁺, glucagon⁺ microadenoma with CK7⁺ epithelium in a stroma-rich environment). (A-E) Detection of glucagon⁺ microadenoma. A-C show microadenoma (arrow) in vibratome section. Fluorescence tissue map (D) identifies the intra-microadenoma ducts (CK7⁺, green; enlarged in inset i and ii, asterisk). Magenta, glucagon; blue, insulin; white, nuclei. PGP9.5 staining (E, cyan) confirms the islet/neuroendocrine lesion. Red, CD31. (F-M) Confirmation of microadenoma-duct lesion mixture with multiplex CgA, H&E, CD45, and Ki-67 signals. The endocrine-exocrine lesion mixture is associated with stromal accumulation (F-I; asterisk, enlarged area), leukocyte infiltration (J, K; asterisk/arrow, enlarged area), and prominent cell proliferation (L, M; box, enlarged area; blue arrows, Ki-67⁺ nuclei). An adjacent PanIN (within 2 mm) is presented in the next page. Black arrows in F, G, J, L indicate the same microenvironment.

Supplemental Fig. S3-2

Suppl. Fig. S3-2 (related to Fig. 5). **Detection of a PanIN lesion adjacent to the microadenoma in panel A-M (Suppl. Fig. S3-1).** (N-P) Microadenoma and its microenvironment visualized via stereomicroscopy. *N-P* and *A-M* examine the same microenvironment (arrow). Vibratome section *P* is further processed for H&E histology to confirm the PanIN lesion. (Q, R) Gross view and enlarged H&E images of PanIN. The gold-standard H&E histology (cyan arrows from *P* to *Q* to *R*, same environment) confirms the low-grade PanIN lesion and peri-lesional stroma. Box in *Q* is magnified in *R* to specify the lesion.